

Activities of Teachers Uzbekistan during the Harsh Years of War

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Abstract:

The article analyzes the activity of teachers, the state and problems that arose in the sphere of education, especially in the system of public education and measures to overcome them in wartime conditions.

Keywords: World War II, Great Patriotic War, front, rear, patriotism, internationalism, education, school, teachers, teaching staff, craft schools.

From the first months of the Second World War, all sectors of the national economy of Uzbekistan were restructured and directed to military needs, including public education. During the Great Patriotic War of 1941-1945, the role, prestige, influence and, most importantly, responsibility of a numerous group of intellectuals - teachers, who are the engineers of the human spirit, increased as never before. Workers of public education along with all workers of the country were able to make a worthy contribution to the fulfillment of all duties throughout the war time.

Under wartime conditions, the development of public education was of great importance. The public education authorities of Uzbekistan faced the difficult task of reorganizing the work of its entire system, since during this difficult period the country needed highly qualified personnel more than ever. Representatives of public education, in addition to carrying out educational work in accordance with wartime requirements, intensified propaganda work among the population, which won the respect of the people. During the crucial period of the war, hundreds of teachers were engaged in propaganda and agitation. With their direct participation throughout the country organized conversations, collective listening to radio broadcasts and reading newspapers. In addition, reports, lectures and talks were given to the population.

A considerable part of the workers of public education were drafted into the ranks of the active army, and on the shoulders of those who remained were entrusted a number of difficult tasks at the

same time: to continue compulsory primary education and the expansion of seven-year education in rural and urban areas, to take all necessary measures to maintain the contingent of schoolchildren, especially high school students; to create all necessary conditions for the education of students employed in production, evening and correspondence courses; to assist collective and state farms in agricultural work, to manage the r At the same time, a number of difficulties had to be overcome in solving such complex tasks.

Under the new wartime conditions, the government demanded that workers in the sphere fulfill all plans for both education and production at the same time. The shortage of material resources, in particular the lack of school buildings, textbooks, and personnel, further complicated the work of the education sector. The 360 city school buildings built before the war were turned into dormitories, hospitals, hospitals and orphanages for evacuees. For example, in the city of Tashkent alone, 42 school buildings were vacated for evacuated enterprises and hospitals. In many urban schools, students were forced to study in three shifts, often adding a fourth shift - evening courses. There was a shortage of necessary school furniture, textbooks, school supplies, glass for windows, miscellaneous furniture and fuel. The lack of technical workers made it difficult to repair school buildings in a timely manner. Teenagers became the main breadwinners for orphaned families. Thousands of children were forced to drop out of school to support their families.

With the outbreak of war in Uzbekistan, as well as throughout the Soviet state, budget allocations for public education were reduced. Since in the early years of the war the bulk of the state budget was spent on defense, this caused a sharp reduction in the budget allocated to social and cultural spheres. For example, in 1940, 561317 rubles were allocated, in 1941 - 538214 rubles, and in 1942 - 461588 rubles. Beginning in 1943, funding for public education began to increase again, as the country's defense capabilities were significantly strengthened during this period.

There were many school teachers among the evacuees during the war. Teachers were given special attention. They were provided with housing, food, clothing and other basic necessities, their children were placed in kindergartens. In 1943, 100 thousand rubles were allocated for the material support of evacuated teachers.

Short-term courses were organized at enterprises to improve the qualifications of women and teenagers who took the place of workers who had gone to the front, and the role of factory education and craft schools in training working youth increased. On July 15, 1943, the Soviet government issued a decree "On the training of adolescents working in enterprises". Since October 1 of this year, schools for working teenagers were opened in cities and working settlements. But there were a number of difficulties in opening these schools. There was a shortage of school buildings, teachers, textbooks, and school equipment.

With the help and support of the workers, the staff of the People's Education Department paid great attention to the repair of school buildings and provided them with fuel. They tried to provide students with school supplies, clothes and shoes. State and collective farms provided foodstuffs, school cafeterias worked, hot meals were prepared. Funds for compulsory general education were organized on the part of patron organizations and parents' committees to provide free food for children and textbooks. Teachers were not overwhelmed by the hardships of the war, they bravely overcame all difficulties. Much attention was paid to improving the material status of teachers, their prestige and role.

Teachers played an important role in the development of public education Accordingly, the state attached great importance to the training of teaching staff and their improvement. During the war years, with the majority of teachers leaving for the front, their number sharply decreased. For example, in the 1940-1941 school year in Uzbekistan there were 36267 teachers, and in the 1942-1943 school year - 30616 [2].

In the 1943-1944 school year, their number decreased by 6651 compared to the 1940-1941 school year. Despite the measures taken, the need for teachers in schools was not satisfied, by the 1945-1946 school year there were 36782 teachers working in schools. Before the beginning of the war, the republic lacked more than 10 thousand teachers. Schools in Uzbekistan needed 6,700 teachers, only schools in Kashkadarya province needed more than 500 teachers.

The war years saw great changes in the number and quality of teachers. The departure of a large number of experienced teachers to the active army and other work led to even greater difficulties. Women and young people were attracted to short-term training courses for training.

The work of schools was also complicated by the fact that on the eve of the war the transition from the Latin alphabet to the Russian alphabet and the publication of new textbooks and teaching aids were planned for the 1941-1942 school year. With the outbreak of war this plan was not realized. However, despite the difficulties of the war, the work to educate the younger generation in the spirit of patriotism and internationalism did not diminish, but intensified. The people provided comprehensive assistance to the work of public education bodies and the upbringing of the younger generation. A number of measures were taken to train teachers, improve educational work, conduct spiritual and physical education, and teach schoolchildren a profession and vital skills.

During the war years, the number of teachers in Uzbekistan decreased by 12,000. 357 schools in the republic did not work due to the shortage of teaching staff. In 1942, out of 5,299 young specialists who graduated from pedagogical institutes, only 2,969 were sent to work in schools. The rest were drafted into the army. During the war years, the proportion of the rest were drafted into the army. The proportion of female teachers increased from 33.4 percent to 55.3 percent. Women became the main force in all sectors [1; p.12].

In the 1941-1942 school year, 550 pedagogical personnel were required for general education schools in Uzbekistan. Of these, 184 were in Tashkent city, 69 in Fergana province, 64 in Samarkand province, and 57 cadres each in Namangan and Bukhara provinces. There were 1,869 applications for recruitment of teachers for incomplete comprehensive schools. The majority of applications were received in Bukhara Province - 403 teachers. In the 1941-1942 school year, 5,402 teachers worked in Uzbekistan, of whom 5,299 had recently graduated from higher education institutions. In Tashkent province alone, 1,112 teachers were hired that year, of whom 1,092 had graduated from higher education institutions. In the 1941-1942 school year secondary schools with Russian-language education were fully provided with teaching staff [6]. In 1944, 5000 teachers were trained on different courses. 15000 students studied at correspondence departments of pedagogical institutes and educational institutions.

In January 1942, the SNK of the USSR and the Central Committee of the Communist Party of the Uzbek SSR adopted resolutions "On the training of teachers for schools of the Uzbek SSR", and on November 1, 1943, "On improving the training of pedagogical staff". Certain work was done to ensure the implementation of the decisions. For example, 21,000 women teachers were trained during the war years. Hundreds of teachers, faithful to their profession and having great experience, received high awards for achievements in the field of education and labor organization during the war. Dozens of teachers were awarded the Order of the Badge of Honor, as well as the titles "Honored Teacher of Uzbekistan" and "Certificates of Merit".

In connection with the decree "On Improving the Training of Pedagogical Personnel", special attention was paid to the training of teachers from the local population, especially women. The directions of pedagogical institutes were expanded. A number of women's educational institutions were established. In order to accelerate the training of teachers, the period of study in pedagogical colleges was reduced from three years to two. Teacher training courses were organized at these colleges. In 1941, the Karshi Pedagogical School trained 90 teachers, and in November, due to necessity, the school was closed and joined to the Bukhara Pedagogical School No. 15, and the

building of the Karshi School was used for military purposes. In 1943, the Karshi Pedagogical School was reopened and about a hundred students were admitted. Initially, the school had 130 students. In January 1944, a correspondence department was opened at the pedagogical school, and 130 inexperienced teachers improved their qualifications during vacations. In 1945, 193 students were enrolled in the correspondence department, 46 of them women and 147 men. By the end of the year, Kashkadarya Province had an opportunity to strengthen teacher training. At the Karshi Pedagogical College, a training department was established with a year-long course of 30 students.

On June 16, 1945, a decision was made to establish a branch of the Bukhara Teachers' Institute in the city of Karshi and to admit students for the 1945-1946 academic year. It stated about opening of the branch of Bukhara Teachers' Institute in Karshi city from June 15, 1945 and admission of 120 students to the branch, as well as about creation of the following departments: history-philology, physics-mathematics, medical-geography. Teachers without higher education began to study at the correspondence department of the Bukhara Pedagogical Institute, students were exempted from tuition fees and provided with free meals.

During the war years, higher educational institutions and pedagogical colleges of the republic trained 9,277 teachers, of whom only 4,126 were of Uzbek nationality. In the 1943-1944 academic year, the Bukhara Pedagogical Institute and its branches in Shafrikon and Gijduvan districts also trained personnel for schools in Kashkadarya province. Out of 115 cadres who graduated from these institutes, 36 teachers were sent to Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya provinces. In the first three years of the war Bukhara Pedagogical and Teacher Training Institute and its branches trained 380 teachers for Bukhara, Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya provinces, and for all the years of the war 610 teachers. In 1944-1945 Bukhara Pedagogical School trained 337 teachers, 920 pedagogical staff were trained at various courses.

Short-term preparatory teacher training courses for women with secondary education were organized at schools in district centers. There were two forms of these courses: the first was to train teachers for students in grades I-IV; the second was to train teachers in various subjects for grades V-VII. The activities of these courses continued throughout the war. However, even this could not fully satisfy the need of educational institutions for pedagogical personnel. Another method of teacher training was used. Girls who graduated from school with honors were attached to experienced teachers and taught professional skills. In addition, teachers went to one school in the first half of the week and taught in another school in the second half. Short-term courses were opened to train teachers for primary grades.

The main source of teacher training in this period was the opening of three-month and six-month pedagogical courses at all pedagogical and teacher training institutes and pedagogical colleges. In particular, groups for training teachers of Uzbek and Russian languages for grades 1-4 were opened at pedagogical colleges. They were provided with experienced teachers.

The courses were mainly attended by young men and women who had completed grades 7-8. In the first years of the war, 71 teachers for primary grades were trained in Kasan district of Kashkadarya province. 37 of them were girls and women who had completed short-term 2.5-month courses. In 1943, 585 people who successfully completed the six-month courses started teaching children different subjects in the schools of the region. Thus, during the war years 21 thousand people took short-term pedagogical courses and replaced the personnel who had left for the active army. During these years methodical evenings on different subjects were organized to improve the qualification of young teachers. In the period from 1941 to 1943 16000 teachers were trained. [5; p.35].

Experienced teachers disseminated their experience among the youth through periodicals. In the cities of Karshi and Shakhrysyabz, lectures on methodological topics were systematically organized.

The need for pedagogical personnel was partially met by those evacuated to Uzbekistan. By January 1943, 2108 teachers evacuated from the occupied territories were working in Uzbek schools, of

whom 869 came from Ukraine, 641 from Russia and 213 from Belarus. 60% of Russian language teachers were from among the evacuees. Teachers evacuated from Ukraine, Belorussia, western Russia and other European republics primarily taught in urban schools, while in Uzbek schools they taught classes in Russian and foreign languages, partly in physical education and military science. Much attention was paid to the organization of Russian classes in national schools. Since September 1942, the Government of Uzbekistan allowed the organization of classes in rural schools with the number of 20 pupils for grades 5-7 and 25 pupils for grades 8-10. In the Russian classes of some schools the number of pupils was even smaller.

The struggle to provide the republic's schools with teaching staff continued, most teachers who had moved to other sectors of the economy and culture in the early years of the war were returned to their profession, and a system of teacher reservations was introduced. On December 25, 1944, the Council of People's Commissars of Uzbekistan adopted a special decree "On the state of public education and the activity of schools in Kashkadarya province", which clearly stated that teachers who left school were not allowed to take other jobs. In 1944-1945 academic year 1273 teachers in the republic, who moved to other branches of national economy, were returned to their jobs, and in Bukhara and Kashkadarya provinces 340 teachers returned to schools. Despite the difficulties of the war, significant changes took place in the provinces and districts as a result of the measures taken.

In wartime conditions, due to the shortage of paper, there were real difficulties in publishing the documents of the People's Education, in particular, working programs, lesson plans, textbooks, manuals and others. Due to the lack of paper, the People's Education Committee was unable to reprint the curricula for the 1941-1942 school year. The new programs for Uzbek language and literature, foreign languages, as well as other normative documents were also not reprinted. This required 1 ton of paper.

Providing the remote regions of Uzbekistan with pedagogical personnel has become one of the most serious problems. Accordingly, appeals were made to higher authorities to establish local teacher training colleges. On November 20, 1943, the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Uzbekistan (b) rejected the appeal of Surkhandarya region in the formation of a teacher training institute in the city of Termez, in order to provide educational institutions with teaching staff [7].

This situation is explained by the following: firstly, the lack of scientific and pedagogical personnel to establish a pedagogical institute, secondly, the lack of a base for opening a pedagogical institute in Termez, as well as the lack of educational buildings, dormitories for students, lack of necessary equipment, thirdly, one of the reasons for refusal was the establishment of pedagogical institutes in Karakalpakstan and Khorezm in 1944. Moreover, the Termez Pedagogical College failed to fulfill the state plan for several years in a row. In 1944, the teachers' institute was transformed into a pedagogical institute. Until that time, the Institute for Teacher Professional Development, established in 1940, worked effectively to improve the quality of the teaching staff. At the same time, there was an acute shortage of 10th grade graduates in the region.

The education of teachers working in the education system was insufficient. In the 1943-1944 school year in Uzbekistan, 63% of elementary school teachers had incomplete secondary education, and 1/3 of teachers in various subjects were graduates of six-month courses. Of the 32170 teachers working in the public education system, 8884 had higher or incomplete higher education. The government was forced to take measures to increase the number of teachers. During the war, the number of students at pedagogical institutes increased by 20%. Two-year teacher training courses were opened at the Central Asian State University, pedagogical institutes, and teacher training institutes.

From January 1, 1943, correspondence departments were established at the Central Asian State University, the Tashkent State Pedagogical Institute, and the Samarkand Institute of Teachers. By the Decree of the Government of the USSR of December 18, 1943 "On measures to deepen the

system of correspondence pedagogical education" correspondence departments were opened in all institutes and educational institutions. In connection with the decision of the Council of People's Commissars of December 18, 1943 "On measures to strengthen the system of correspondence pedagogical education" the correspondence education of pedagogical staff was strengthened. On January 1, 1944 a correspondence department was organized at the Karshi Pedagogical Institute. Here, 130 young inexperienced teachers were trained during the vacation period.

In addition, the People's Commissariat of Education of the Republic instructed to strengthen the admission of teachers without higher education to the correspondence department of the Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute. For the full convenience of correspondence students on June 15, 1945 at the branch of the Bukhara Pedagogical Institute opened a consular post in the city of Karshi. This point and the branch conducted its activities in the building of the school named after Akhunbabaev, located on Kuchabog Street. The head of the scientific department of the pedagogical school Kuramshin was appointed as the head of this point. In 1945, 14 pedagogical institutes and 14 pedagogical colleges had correspondence departments. In 1945, 1,353 students studied at correspondence departments. However, the number of correspondence students in pedagogical universities was 52% of the planned number. The reason for this was the negligence of the responsible local managers engaged in this work. In 1945, 9657 students studied at the correspondence department of 14 pedagogical universities and 14 pedagogical schools of the republic. Much attention was paid to the material situation of teachers and to the improvement of their prestige and role in society. The state took some measures to protect teachers.

In August 1943, in accordance with the Soviet government's decree "On Increasing the Salaries of Teachers and Other Public Education Workers," teachers' monthly salaries were increased by an average of 30-50%. In addition, special stores and canteens were opened for intellectuals and teachers of urban and rural schools, rural teachers were provided with land plots, seeds for sowing, and loans for housing construction. Teachers who set an example in teaching and educating the younger generation received material and spiritual support. Workers of the sphere of national education, teachers and pedagogues, students, employees with the help and support of collective farmers and workers repaired school buildings and school supplies. A large number of schools throughout the republic were repaired by teachers and with the support of the population.

Teachers constantly transferred a certain amount from their salaries to the defense fund. In 1942, teachers of Andijan region allocated 50 thousand rubles for the construction of the tank column "People's Teacher", teachers of the city of Andijan - 60 thousand rubles, and teachers of Markhamat district - 41.5 thousand rubles. [3].

In addition, teachers and schoolchildren visited military hospitals, read books to the wounded, helped write letters, performed various amateur art concerts. Also schoolchildren took an active part in sending various gifts for soldiers to the front.

In June 1942, schoolchildren in Uzbekistan sent 30 wagons of food and clothing to schoolchildren in Leningrad, and in 1943 - 20 wagons of food and clothing. The initiative started in 1941 by pupils of secondary school No. 115 in Tashkent covered the whole country. All schoolchildren of the republic fully supported the noble initiative of Tashkent schoolchildren to collect scrap metal and other things to strengthen the country's defense capability. Schoolchildren of Uzbekistan collected 32,223 tons of non-ferrous metals for the first 9 months of the war instead of the planned 936 tons. Children from Andijan region collected 380 tons, Surkhandarya region 796 tons, Tashkent region 871 tons of scrap metal. 2525 tons of scrap metal were collected and handed over to the state in a short period of time all over Uzbekistan. From April 1 to April 15, 1942 the youth of Fergana region collected 774 thousand tons of scrap metal. Despite all the difficulties and hardships of wartime, schoolchildren and students throughout the republic showed a true sense of patriotism. [4; p.].

Teacher registration was conducted haphazardly and the work in this area was inadequate. School directors were hardly engaged in filling in the teachers' documents. Neither the educational background of incoming teachers nor their length of service could be determined from the documents. For example, neither the City Department of Public Education nor the City Statistical Department could provide the exact number of teachers in 117 schools in Tashkent who worked during the war years. In addition, despite the fact that the Tashkent Department of Public Education issued an order not to exceed 52 hours of teachers' teaching load, school principals and heads of science departments in Kuibyshev, Kirov, Stalin and Lenin districts exceeded the teachers' hours. For example, the Russian language teacher of School No. 60 in Tashkent City, Chubukova, had an overloaded work schedule. This situation was observed in almost all schools of the republic.

Nevertheless, the government made great efforts to improve teachers' material status, prestige and prestige. Teachers who set an example in teaching and educating the younger generation received material and spiritual support. Hundreds of teachers, who glorified their profession and accumulated great experience, received high awards for their achievements in the field of education and organization of work during the war years. Dozens of teachers were awarded the Order of the Badge of Honor, as well as the titles of "Honored Teacher of Uzbekistan" and "Certificates of Merit".

The study of the sphere of education in Uzbekistan during the war years has led to the following conclusions: first, from the first years of the war, public education was oriented to meet the needs and requirements of the war, the majority of workers were mobilized to the active army, and students of schools, colleges and universities were involved in production and field work. The state entrusted the public education departments with a number of complex tasks, which required active participation in both educational and national economy activities. During the war years, students and teachers made a huge contribution to the victory over the common enemy. Simultaneously engaged in education and labor, they became the main force in fulfilling the plans of agricultural and industrial enterprises. The youth of Uzbekistan, together with the evacuated youth, worked hard for victory, for the Motherland, for peace, well-being and freedom.

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